

varietal release committee in 1985 as TPS1. This is the first variety released from the Thirupathisaram PES, Tamil Nadu.

TPS1, a derivative of IR8/ Kattisamba, is semitall (110 cm), matures in 110-115 d, and has higher

yield potential than local Kattisamba. It is medium tillering with light green foliage and good panicle exertion. Panicles are long and compact.

Average grain yields of 5.0 t/ha, 17.8% more than those of Kattisamba, have been recorded. Production

potential is 7.8 t/ha. Average straw yield is 9.2 t/ha. The grain is short bold with a red kernel closely resembling that of Kattisamba. It possesses good cooking quality.

TPS1 has field tolerance for stem borer. □

Rice variety resistant to gall midge (GM) and bacterial blight (BB) released in Madhya Pradesh (MP), India

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Usha, a semidwarf high yielding rice variety with resistance to GM and BB, has been released for general cultivation in MP. Usha is derived from IR22/W1263. It resembles IR22 in plant type. IR22 is susceptible to GM and BB but Usha and W1263 are

Table 1. Reaction to BB (PXO 61) of F₁ and F₂ progenies from crosses of TN1 with Usha and W1263. MP, India.

Cross	Disease reaction			
	F ₁	F ₂		
		Resist ant (no.)	Susceptible (no.)	x ² 3:1
TN1/Usha	Resistant	671	245	1:40
TN1/W1263	Resistant	287	113	2.08

resistant at Raipur, MP. A single dominant gene *GMI* conferred Usha's resistance to the GM biotype.

A single dominant gene also conferred resistance to BB (Table 1). Usha and W1263 have the same allelic gene *Xa-4* as IR22 has (Table 2).

Table 2. Reaction to BB (PXO 61) of F₁ and F₂ progenies from crosses of IR22 with Usha and W1263. MP, India.

Cross	Disease reaction		
	F ₁	F ₂	
		Resistant (no.)	Susceptible (no.)
IR22/Usha	Resistant	856	0
IR22/W1263	Resistant	406	0

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Influence of vegetative growth duration on grain grade

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The vegetative growth (VG) period of BPI-76, a photoperiod-sensitive cultivar, was altered to 45, 65, 85, and 105 d by manipulating photoperiod. Plants were grown in 4-liter plastic pots in the glasshouse. Each pot contained 3.5 kg soil fertilized with 4 g ammonium sulfate, 2 g solophos, and 2 g muriate of potash. Five plants per pot were grown under 24-h photoperiod. Sowings were staggered.

Plants were transferred to 10-h photoperiod so that climatic conditions during reproductive and ripening phases were similar. Grain grade was determined by the specific gravity method.

Grain yield was higher with 45 and 65 d VG (see table) and gradually

Influence of vegetative growth duration on number of different grades of grain per hill.^a IRRRI, 1986.

Parameter	Vegetative growth duration			
	45 d	65 d	85 d	105 d
Grain yield/hill (g)	6.8 a	6.2 a	5.4 b	4.4 c
Panicles/hill	3.8 a	3.1 b	2.7 c	3.1 d
Total spikelets	459 a	429 ab	381 bc	336 c
Empty spikelets	54 a	72 a	70 a	74 a
Poor grains ^b	(11)	(16)	(18)	(22)
Average ^b	46 a	44 a	34 a	24 a
Good ^b	(8)	(10)	(9)	(7)
High density grains ^b	157 a	115 a	42 b	38 b
Total grains	(28)	(32)	(10)	(11)
	200 a	198 a	233 a	193 a
	(49)	(41)	(66)	(59)
	1.5 a	1.0 a	2.2 a	0.7 a
	(4)	(2)	(.5)	(.3)
	405 a	358 b	311 c	262 d
	(89)	(84)	(83)	(78)

^aFigures in parentheses are percent of respective grades of total spikelets. In a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bPoor grains = collected from 1.0-1.06 specific gravity; average grains, 1.08-1.12 specific gravity; good grains, 1.14 to 1.10 specific gravity; and high density grains, 1.20 specific gravity.

decreased with increased growth duration. The higher grain yield at 45 and 65 d was due mainly to high panicle numbers, fertility percentage, and total grain numbers per hill.

High density (HD) grain yield (grains which submerge at 1.20 sp gr) was not related to VG duration. BPI-76 produced hardly any HD grains; production of HD grain did not differ

significantly among growth durations.

For maximum spikelet formation, 45 to 65 d VG duration appears to be advantageous; for HD grains, longer VG duration is not a disadvantage. All durations studied produced almost similar percentages of good grade grain. Longer VG was associated with

lower total grain numbers, resulting in lower yields. VG up to 65 d (total growth duration of 110 d) was associated with moderately high numbers of good grade grain and fairly high numbers of other grain grades.

It should be possible to combine the

character of high numbers of HD grain with any VG duration. For higher potential yields, a VG duration of 45 d (total growth duration of 91 d) is not limiting. It is possible to combine the character of HD grain with very short growth duration. □

Dormancy in some early and medium duration varieties

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The dormancy of some early and medium duration high-yielding varieties (HYVs) grown under upland, midland, and lowland conditions in Dakshina Kannada region with heavy rainfall conditions was assessed in 1984 and 1985.

The seed samples were collected 30 d after flowering and sun-dried to 13-14% moisture. Germination and dormancy (80% germination) were calculated on 25 seeds/petri dish at

Germination and dormancy of some early and medium duration rice varieties. Brahmavar (DK), India, 1985.

Variety	Duration (d)	Germination ^a (%)						Dormancy ^b
		5 DH ^b		10 DH		20 DH		
		1984	1985	1984	1985	1984	1985	
Rasi	110	87	87	99	100	100	100	—
Jyothi	123	91	95	100	100	—	—	—
Annapoorna	106	45	75	91	97	99	100	10
KKP2	110	53	79	90	92	100	97	10
IET7303	129	70	76	85	88	97	100	10
Shakthi	135	33	56	98	84	98	96	10
Jaya	139	35	56	99	95	—	100	10
Phalguna	149	15	18	30	46	88	88	20

^aDH = days after harvest. ^b80% germination.

10-d intervals, starting 5 d after harvest, with 4 replications.

Rasi and Jyothi were nondormant (see table). Annapoorna, KKP2,

Shakthi, Jaya, and IET7303 recorded 10-d dormancy. Phalguna recorded 20d dormancy. □

Ratoon tillering in short-duration rice varieties

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A set of the 1985 International Rice Yield Nursery-Early was grown during 1985-86 dry season at Malda. The main crop was sown on 24 Nov 1985 and transplanted 16 Jan 1986. Cool temperature during Nov-Mar usually extends crop duration.

After harvest, irrigation water and 20-10-10 kg NPK/ha were applied. Varieties with higher hill regeneration

Ratoon tillering in shortduration rice varieties. Maida, West Bengal, India, 1985-86.

Regenerated hills (%)	Entries (no.)	Ratoon tillers (no./hill)		Main crop days to 50% flowering
		Range	Average	
0-60	7	1-2	1	133-146
61-70	1	3	3	133
71-80	5	2-5	4	133-146
81-90	3	5-7	6	130-143
91-100	11	5-13	8	133-146

also showed more ratoon tillers/hill (see table).

BW295-5, C662083, IR18348-36-3-3 (IR64), IR25621-135-1-1, IR29658-69-2-1, IR29725-45-1-1-3, IR31868-64-2-

3-3-3, IR35546-52-3-3-2, SI-P1681032, and SI-PI692033 had higher ratoon tillering ability. Flowering duration of the main crop did not affect ratoon tillering ability. □

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